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Experimental and Computational Studies on Catalytic Activity of Novel Adenine-Based Nano Cu(I) Polymers in Regioselective Synthesis of 1,4-Disubstituted 1,2,3-Triazoles

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Abstract

Cu(I) nanoparticles were immobilized on modified poly(styrene-co-maleic anhydride) by Adenine with loading of 23.83% (w/w) of heterogeneous catalyst. The prepared nano catalyst was characterized by FTIR, ¹H-NMR, SEM-EDAX, ICP-OES, TEM, BET and XRD. The catalytic activity of this novel heterogeneous Cu(I) nano particles was successfully examined in the regioselective synthesis of 1,4-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles via click reaction to give the corresponding products in satisfactory yield (78–87%). The heterogeneous catalyst was readily separated from reaction mixture and reused at least in four consecutive runs without loss of appreciable catalytic activity. Furthermore, a series of systematic computational studies was joint with experiment to answer some fundamental questions regarding the structure, stability, and nature of interactions in the novel inhomogeneous coordination nano catalyst.

Keyword: 1,2,3-triazoles, Click reaction, Cu (I) adenine, DFT calculations, Regioselectivity, Catalysts, Styrene, Computational studies, DFT calculation, Heterogeneous catalyst, Poly(styrene-co-maleic anhydride), Reaction mixture, Regioselective synthesis, Catalyst activity